
MEDICINAL SIGNIFICANCE OF PLANTS MENTIONED IN HADITH LITERATURE AND CONTEMPORARY TIMES: AN ANALYSIS

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ABSTRACT

Several kinds of plants and herbs are found in different regions of the world. All the plants have significant economic, environmental, nutritional, and medicinal value. Many plants and herbs with medicinal properties have been mentioned in the hadith literature. Prophet Muhammad (SAW) has advised using various plants in His sayings as a remedy for illness. According to modern scientific reports, Plants contain carbohydrates, minerals, and vitamins. Plants are be have been used to cure diseases from the beginning of man`s history. Cure and diseases have a deep relationship with each other. With the passage of time health curative system was updated by hadith literature. Plants with their medicinal values and pharmacological actions can be seen in the holy sayings of the prophet Muhammad (SAW). Herbal medicines are considered hope and a symbol of safety for humanity. In fact, people are returning to the natural cure for diseases in the current pandemic environment. our major objective of this study is to highlight the importance, nutritional and medicinal properties of some selected herbs and plants mentioned in hadith literature. Furthermore, this research analyzes ingredients, plants' classification, and the natural cures of diseases in contemporary times.

Key Words: Hadith Literature, Plants, Herbs, Medicinal properties, Classification.

Introduction

The Lord of the Universe has created innumerable plants and herbs to fulfill the social, economic, nutritional, and medicinal needs of human life in this world. The history of plants and herbs is as old as human beings. Ancient plants are still in use as remedies for ailments today. In modern times, scientific research has discovered hundreds of medical and nutritional benefits of plants mentioned in the holy text of hadith literature, most herbs and plants are being used as cures likewise Ginger for

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cough conditions, Banana for diarrhea, and pomegranate for intestinal bleeding. The medicinal properties of herbs and plants have gained the attention and interest of biochemists, pharmacologists, botanists, and herb-drug specialists. So, they are all taking a keen interest to search out the health benefits and other medicinal effects of herbs and plants. According to recent research reports, there is a number of plants at least (50000) a thousand different herbal medicines are being used at the global level at current times." health issue is one of the biggest challenges of the current time. Modern Man is facing various infectious diseases. The rise of diseases is alarming. The sayings of Prophet Muhammad (SAW) about healthy lifestyles and healing plants can play a key role in solving issues of current health issues.

Research Methodology

Quantitative and qualitative research methodology has been adopted in this research work. Mostly primary sources were taken. But some secondary sources were also used in some places. In this research work, the medicinal and nutritional values of herbs and plants have been discussed in light of modern medical science. A lot number of herbs and plants with their medication values were mentioned in Hadith literature but here only seven plants have been analyzed.

Literature Review

Researchers have performed commendable work on the significant role of plants & herbs in the cure of human beings. Mr. Muhammad Abid Nadeem (2005) presented the properties of plants as well as animals in the light of modern science and Quranic teachings in his Ph.D. thesis. Researcher Ghazala Salim (2007) has discussed the medicinal importance of plants in light of Tibb-e-Nabvi in her doctorate dissertation. Imam As-Suyuti`s Tibb-e-Nabvi (Medicine of the Prophet) was a collection of wise medical sayings of the prophet Muhammad (SAW). Professor Rashid Bhikha & Dr. Ashraf Dockrat have compiled a book "Medicine of the Prophet". Its 16th chapter sheds light on the history of the medicinal and nutritional properties of plants. Imam Ibn-e- Qayyum Al-Jauziyah, in his book Tibb-e-Nabvi (medicine of the prophet), has elaborated medicinal properties of plants and natural cures of various diseases in the light of texts of hadith literature.

In addition to the above said research scholars, some other people have also highlighted the medicinal significance of herbs and plants mentioned in light of Islamic teachings. All these authors tried their best to discuss the medicinal importance of plants and herbs in a good manner so that the public may get benefit as more as possible. Of course, many books and huge literature are already available in the market. But similarity among plants and the healing temperament of plants is the basic issue, so, plants` healing temperament and classification with their medicinal benefits have been discussed.

Discussion

The role of plants and herbs in medicine is very important in different diseases now people are returning to natural treatment due to the side effects of chemical drugs Improvement of herbal medicine is carried on in the world. Herbs and plants were collected from different parts of the world The development of herbal medicines collected from different parts of the world was revived and improved during the golden age of Islamic civilization by medical pioneers like Ibn Sina, Al-Biruni, Al-Zhrawi, Al-Razi. Much of this knowledge returned to Europe during the Renaissance \ period. While herbal medicine has declined in the past few decades due to the advancement of modern traditional medicine, the future of herbal medicine is assured, as nature has provided man with numerous, if not all, plants. from some form of biological activity, intended or otherwise. At the same time, the development of new traditional medicine of nature is beginning to dry up. Indeed, there is a major resurgence of interest in the use of herbal medicines, particularly in the long-term treatment of chronic disorders. This is partly due to dissatisfaction with the extensive side effects associated with conventional medicine.

Plants are significant due to medication, providing humanity with food, habitats, dress, cosmetics, and curative facilities for many diseases that trouble human life. The use of plants for healing is the firstborn form of medicine. Mention of herbs and plants is found in all the Islamic books relating to care and health. The history of plants begins with the history of Hazrat Adam (A. S) according to holy texts of the Divine book Quran.

It is stated in chapter 7 of the Quran:” *God said O Adam you and your wife live and eat freely wherever you like but do not go near the tree otherwise you will be among the transgressors*”ⁱ

1.GINGER...ZINGIBER OFFICINALE

English Name	Ginger
Arabic Name:	Zanjabil
Kingdom	Plantae
Division	Magnoliophyte
Class	Liliopsid
Family	Zingiberaceae
Genus	Ginger Mill
Species	Zingiber officinal
Scientific Name	Zingiber officinale
Habit and Habitat:	Perennial Cultivated herb and has an underground stem.
Distribution.	Bangladesh, Yamane, Oman, Sera lone, India, and Pakistan
Parts used	Fruit and roots

Medicinal use

Zinger is useful in intestinal pain, stomach disturbance, impotence, digestive problem, intestinal infections, and swellings. It shows better results in dog biting, diarrhea, and impotency.

*"The temperament of ginger is dry in the second degree, hot and dry in the third. Ginger develops sexual strength, dissolves secretions, phlegm, and thickness, due to hotness, helps in digestion, powerful tonic. one companion of the Prophet gives him a jar of ginger which was delivered to all companions to eat."*²

It contains excess dampness. It is an aid to digestion, strengthens sexual intercourse, and dissolves wind. If the purgative is weak or if there is edema, then its reaction is strengthened by the addition of ginger. It renders fluid the thickness of phlegm. A confection of ginger soothes the stomach. It is a tonic in old age. *"From Abu Said comes the story that a Byzantine emperor once gave the Prophet a jar containing ginger and he made all of his Companions eat a piece of it."*³

*"It is used for the cure of diseases in contemporary times. It is useful in the cure of Painkilling, anorexia, anti-allergenic, anti-bacterial, Anti-convulsant, Anti-fungal, Anti-spasmodic, Anti-Tumor, anti-ulcer, Swelling Asthma, mucus, anxieties, bellyache, mobbing, stultification, chilling effects, on the body, cough spasms, Diarrhea, Gastric stimulating, dog bits, indigestion, effective in reducing the effect of morning illness in pregnant females. Temperature flu, digestive, anti-secretory, annoyance, heart tremor, upsurge urine production, indigestion, infection diseases, duodenal pain, intestinal bulge, loss of hunger, gesture, disease, muscular ache, biliousness, rheumatoid arthritis, sexual faintness, sinusitis, sore throats, wrenches stomach, disorder, swelling energy 354kcal/100g."*⁴

Ginger is a diffusive energizer that is warming by expanding the fringe course; a crisis cure at whatever point prompt excitement is required, an expert spice for easing queasiness and movement disorder; an anesthetic in gastric and gastrointestinal aggravation; a carminative and hostile to convulsive in the intestinal system; diaphoretic for advancing sweat in hot circumstances; betting fiery especially valuable in rheumatic circumstances that advantage from heat; against microbial rubefacient and a solid emmenagogue.

Ginger is mentioned in Quran. It shows the importance of ginger in the religion of Islam. It is stated in Quran as under:

*"There they shall be served with cups of wine flavored with ginger."*⁵

Ginger is also mentioned in the text of Hadith literature. A tradition of the prophet shows that Ginger was used by prophet Muhammad (SAW) and His companions.

It is stated in a hadith of Prophet Muhammad (SAW) as under:

“It is narrated by Hazrat Abu Saeed Al-Khudri that the Emperor of Rome offered a jar of ginger as a gift to Holy Prophet (SAW). I also got a piece of it that I ate”⁶

Nutritional value of Ginger (100g)

Nutrients	Amount	Nutrients	Amount
Proteins	1.8g	Phytosterols	15mg
Ash	0.8g	Phytosterols	15mg
Total Calories	80g	Calories from Carbohydrates	68mg
Calories from fats	6.3	Calories from Proteins	5.1mg
Total Carbohydrates	18g	Dietary Fiber	2g
Sugar	1.7g	Saturated Fat	203mg
Total Fats	750mg	Omega-6Fatty Acid	120mg
Monounsaturated	154mg	Vitamin E	260Ug
Omega-3Fatty Acid	34mg	Thiamin	25Ug
Vitamin C	5mg	Niacin	750Ug
Vitamin K	0.1Ug	Folate	11mg
Riboflavin	34Ug	Choline	28.8mg
Vitamin B6	160Ug	Iron	600Ug
Pantothenic Acid	203Ug	Phosphorus	34mg
Calcium	16mg	Sodium	13mg
Magnesium	43mg	Copper	226Ug
Potassium	415mg	Selenium	0.7Ug
Zinc	340Ug	Manganese	229Ug

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2. ONION---ALLIUM CEPA

English Name: Onion
 Arabic Name: Basal
 Kingdom: Plantae
 Division: Embruohyta
 Class: Magnoliopsida
 Order: Asparaguses
 Family: Amaryllidaceae
 Genus: Allium L
 Species: Allium cepa L
 Habit and Habitat: Annual cultivated herb
 Distribution: Pakistan, China, Russia, India, America, and Europe
 Part used: Bulb, seeds. And leaves

Medicinal uses

It is beneficiary in diarrhea, cholera, stomach diseases, and Antidote, and play an important role in fever, throat infection ear pain, influenza, and the common cold works in sperm production improvement. Other diseases likewise pile, eye infections appetizer baldness, intestinal diseases, headache, menstruation, and constipation.

Antidote, Stomach diseases, cholera, Diarrhea, Throat infection, common cold, cough, fever, influenza, ear pain, improve sperm production, clear face and skin spots, appetizer, headache, hepatitis, piles, eye diseases baldness, constipation, menstruation, and intestinal diseases.

*"It contains minerals, sugars, cellulose, protein, and essential oil fixed oil. and 80 percent water. Although the amount of essential is low because there are aromatic and tear-producing properties in it likewise onion this is the reaction of amino acid and enzyme alliinase on it."*⁸

"The onion is hot and dry in the third stage."⁹ Chemical properties: It has three components: Sili toxin, Silipakrin, and Selin".¹⁰

"It is a medicine for those who suffer from cold easily which settles in the depth of the nose and eye and spreads quickly to the throat, ear, larynx, and bronchi due to raw phlegm there is running burning water from the nose like fire in all stages of coryza and drains the upper part of the lip"¹¹The temperament of the onion is hot and moist it makes food delicious, moistens semen and cuts mucus. Inhaling it prevents vomiting after taking medicine Eating with onion removes the unpleasant smell,"¹²

"Allium cepa L is help full to control those processes how stats in high age fact likewise cardiovascular tumor promotion which is associated with free radicals."¹³

"Nowadays main use of Bulbous Allium cepa is to prevent changes caused by high age increase in blood pressure, and lack of appetite. It is used as a treatment for bacterial infection, diuretics, stomach ulcers, and dysentery. used in diabetes as sporting medicine."¹⁴ According to China pharmacopeia, its treatment protects from angina pectoris, dyspnea, difficulty breathing, pain full spasmodic, and contraction of the anal. It is also used as an anthelmintic in the treatment of aphrodisiac, carminative, emmenagogue linctus, and as a tonic. it shows better results in the cure of fever, colic, and bruises. Earache cholera, jaundice pimples, sores, and high blood pressure"¹⁵ Its juice is used for making cough syrup which is useful for colds"¹⁶

Onion is stated in Surah Baqra of the Quran as "And when you said,

"Musa, we will not wait for longer ourselves on one food: So, pray your God for us that He may grow vegetables from the earth. Cucumber, wheat, lentil, onion, (He peace and blessing of Allah be upon) do you want to take some things which are inferior instead of better? Go down the city you will find what you ask for and they were sealed with disgrace and the wrath of Allah because they denied it":¹⁷

“It is stated in a Hadith as follows: Narrated by Hazrat Ayesha (RA) the last food which ate Hazrat Muhammad (PBUH) was contained onion.”¹⁸

Food Value of Onion / 100g

Moisture	86.6%	Calcium	47mg
Protein	1.2%	Phosphorus	50mg
Fat	0.1%	Iron	0.7mg
Vitamin C	11mg	Carbohydrate	11.1%
Fiber	0.4%		

3. Garlic---ALLIUM SATIVUM

English Name:	Garlic
Scientific Name	Allium sativum
Arabic Name:	Soom
Kingdom	Plantae
Division	Tracheophyte
Class	Liliopsid
Order	Asparagales
Family:	Amaryllidaceae
Genus	Allium
Species	Allium sativum L
Part used:	Bulb

Medicinal use

It is a curative remedy in wound healing, dog biting, paralysis, peptic cases, asthma, cough, hysteria, paraenesis, intestinal pain worms, headache, and tuberculosis. *“It is useful in cough, whooping cough, bronchitis, fever, facial paralysis, flatulence, colic, stultification, atonic indigestion, helminthiasis, duodenal ulcers, pulmonary and laryngeal tuberculom, ophthalmopathy, cardiopathy, exhaustion, leukoderma, leprosy, panic, piles, backache, otalgia, lumbago, swellings, plexopathy, hepatopathy, pneumopathy, arthralgia, painful eyes, ear pain, and dental consonant caries.”¹⁹*

It is stated in Quran as under:

“And when you said: Musa, we will no longer confine ourselves to a single food: So, pray for us to your Lord that He may bring forth for us of what the earth grows — of its vegetable, its cucumbers, its wheat (garlic), its lentils and its onions.”²⁰

Prophet Muhammad (SAW) stated as follows: *“It is narrated by Hazrat Ali that it is forbidden to eat garlic except when it is cooked.”²¹*

4. Fenugreek--- Trigonella foenum _ graecum

English name	Fenugreek
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Arabic name	Hulba
Scientific Name	Trigonella foenum-graecum
Kingdom	Plantae
Division	Tracheophyte
Class	Magnoliopsida
Order	Fagales
Family Name:	Fabaceae
Genus	Trigonella L-fenugreek
Species	Tefoenum
Parts used	Leaves and seeds

Medicinal use

“Fenugreek is the better remedy for infection of the throat, pain in the body stomach disturbance, pain in the breast, dandruff, diabetes, baldness, gastritis puffiness, body pain, cough, stomach pain, piles, dandruff, baldness, breast pain, infection in lungs, diabetes, ulcer, loose motion, and gas trouble. Powerful tonic, back pain, seeds in powder form used for diabetes, galactagogue i.e., to stimulate milk production in mammary glands, Carminative, Tonic, Aphrodisiac”.²² “The root is applied in the treatment of dropsy.”²³. Its leaf juice is widely used for baldness.” It contains alkaloid trigonelline and essential oil. It plays the role of an anti-diabetic.”²⁴ It is stated in hadith literature as below:

“Mu'adh bin Jabal narrates that the Messenger of Allah (SAW) said, If my Ummah knew the importance of fenugreek, it would buy it equal to its weight in gold.”²⁵

Nutritional value of Fenugreek /100g

Energy	323Kcal	Carbohydrate	58.35g	Sodium	67mg
Protein	23g	Total fat	6.41g	Calcium	176mg
Cholesterol	0mg	Dietary fiber	24.6g	Iron	33.53mg
Folates	54ug	Niacin	1.640mg	Manganese	1.228mg
Pyridoxin	0.600mg	Riboflavin	0.366mg	Selenium	6 3ug
Thiamin	0.322mg	Potassium	770mg	Magnesium	191mg
Vitamin C	3mg	Copper	1.110mg	Phosphorus	296mg
Vitamin A	60ug	Zinc	2.50mg		

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5. FIG---FICUS CARICA

English Name:	Fig
Arabic Name:	Teen
Kingdom;	Plantae
Scientific name;	Focus Carica
Division;	Magnoliophytes
Class;	Magnoliopsida
Order;	Utricles
Family	Moraceae

Genus	Focus L
Species	Focus benzamine L
Part used:	Fruit and oil
Distribution;	Pakistan, Afghanistan, S.W Asia, and Mediterranean Region
Part used;	Leaves, Bark, and oil

Medicinal uses:

The leaves of this beautiful tree are used to make a fragrance with the aroma of wood or musk Dried figs are put into hot water for the softness of their shape figs gradients are high, fiber, potassium, iron, and calcium.

“it is also useful in these diseases’ constipation Hemorrhoid, Asthma, cough, kidney problems skin diseases, Liver ailments, and General debility, it is used as a laxative and diuretic”²⁷ It is stated in Quran as follows:

“I swear by the Fig and the Olive”²⁸

Prophet Muhammad (SAW) says:

“Abu Hurairah narrates that a plate full of figs was gifted to the Messenger of God and He said to his companions to eat. Further said it is undoubtedly the fruit of paradise. Eat it because it removes hemorrhoids and is useful in rheumatism.”²⁹

Nutritional Value of Fig

	Raw figs	Dried figs
Calories	74kcl	249kcl
Protein	0.75g	33g
Lipids	0.3g	0.93g
Dietary	2.9g	9.8g
Sugar	1.26g	47.92g
Calcium	35mg	162mg
Iron	0.37mg	2.03mg
Magnesium	17mg	68mg
Phosphorus	14mg	67mg
Potassium	232mg	680mg
Vitamin C	2mg	1.2mg
Choline	6mg	9mg
Vitamin A	7mcg	9ug
Beta-carotene	85ug	6ug
Lutein and zeaxanthin	9mg	32ug
Vitamin k	4,7ug	15,6ug

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6. Beet roots--- Beta vulgaris

English name	Beetroots
Arabic name	Saliq banjur
Family	Chenopodiaceae
Distribution	Pakistan, Europe, Africa, India North Africa, Europe, and Ireland,

Part used: Roots and leaves

Medicinal use

Temperament: *Beetroot is a vegetable that is similar to a turnip and is found in the ground. It is sweet in taste and hot in temperament*³¹

*"Beetroots has his medicinal properties research has improved that it is useful in piles, cancer, constipation, stomach, sexual impotency, and intestinal inflammation"*³²

Beetroots are beneficiary in skin diseases, eczema, muscle weakness, liver infection, womb diseases, hepatitis, headache, arthritis, vaginal pain liver infection, baldness, and kidney disturbance, it is a remedy to increase the production of human hormones.

It is Anti- tumors, anticancer, and Antioxidant. It is generally used in contemporary herbalism and a decoction produced using the seed has been utilized as a treatment for stomach growth, dryness, and coolness. The seed is professed to treat genital cancers when warmed in water. Jaundice, leukemia, and numerous diseases, including those of the bosom, throat, organs, head, digestion tracts, hung, lip, leg, spleen, rectum, prostate, stomach, and uterine, are accounted for to be treated with the juice or other plant parts. Betaine and anthocyanin are believed to be huge in the trade of synthetic substances between malignant growth cells, while choline and its oxidized type, butane, are two fundamental amines whose non-attendance causes cancers in mice. Ulcers have been dealt with utilizing the juice.

*"It diminishes gastrointestinal intensity for laxative purposes, a decoction is used by people who have hemorrhoids. also, looseness of the bowels, as an emmenagogue, leaves and roots are utilized. Viable plant for treating cat ascariasis. Beet juice was once advised as a treatment for weakness and yellow jaundice as well as a nasal flush for toothaches, ringing ears, and head clearing. It was accepted that beet juice in vinegar could treat dandruff and scurf on the scalp as well as prevent hair from dropping out. It was accepted that the white beet's juice could break up heat-related blockages in the liver and spleen. Beetroot is a vegetable that is similar to a turnip and is found in the ground. It is sweet in taste and hot in temperament."*³³

It is stated in a Hadith of the Prophet (SAW):

*"It is narrated that Abu Hazim told used to feel happiness on Friday I asked him what was the reason for his happiness he replied that there was an old woman of our acquaintance She used to send someone to Buda (Ibn E Musalmah says Buda was a Garden of dates near Madinah) She brings roots of silq from this garden and put them in a pot and add in it barley powder and cooks it after the prayer of Friday we passed by her and she serves us with this delicious food we use to feel happy after eating this food we neither take an afternoon nap nor eat food after the Friday prayer."*³⁴

Prophet Muhammad (SAW) said:

"Umm Mundhir bint Qaia Ansariyyah says once the prophet of God Hazrat Muhammad (May peace be upon him) came upon us Hazrat Ali bin Abu Talib was also

with them who had recently recovered from illness there were hanging some bunches of unripe dates Prophet of Allah was eating. Hazrat Ali went forward for eating then He (PBUH) said to Hazrat Ali, stop you have recently recovered from illness. I made some greens and barley for the Prophet (SAW) then the Messenger of Allah (may peace be upon him) grant peace to Hazrat Ali, take some of it and eat it is better for you.”³⁵

Nutritional Value of Beetroots /100g

Energy	180Kcal	Carbohydrate	956g
Sugars	676g	Fat	0.17g
Dietary fiber	28g	Protein	161g
Vitamin A	Equiv I%	Thiamin (B1)	0.031mg
Beta carotene	2ug	Riboflavin (B2)	0.04mg
Niacin (B3)	0.334mg	Acid (B5)	0.155mg
Vitamin (B6)	0.067mg	Folate (B9)	109ug
Vitamin (C)	4.9mg	Manganese	23mg
Calcium	2%	Iron	0.8mg

³⁶

7. Sweet Flag--- Acorus calamus

English Name Sweet flag
Arabic Name Zarera,- Qudulwai
Family Acoraceae
Distribution: N. and C. America, Europe, Asia.
Part used: Roots

It is stated in a saying of Prophet Muhammad (SAW):

“It is narrated by Ayesha during Hajjat-ul-Wida, I scented Allah`s Prophet Hazrat Muhammad peace be upon him with Zarira with my own hands, when he (PBUH) wears on his Ihram and wear out it”³⁷

Medicinal benefits

“It is considered hot but there is a disposition whether it is light hot or dried hot. It is used in the cure of eye diseases, bellyache, liver, and duodenal disorders, cardiovascular diseases, constipation, eczema, immobility, asthma, frenzy, psychosis, malaria fever, and swelling. It is medically very beneficiary Vomit, anti-spasmodic, flatus-relieving, painkilling, indigestion, and nerve tonic given for heartburn, bellyache, remittent fever, epileptic respiratory ,gritty tumor, and snake bites. It is used against lice and Vermes. It is also used in kidney problems, liver diseases, rheumatism, and skin diseases.”³⁸

Other names are used for the sweet flag as clams, sweet sedges, and myrtle flag (Acorus calamus L.). Despite having its roots in South Asia, it has been effectively transplanted in most parts of the globe, its productive area is deeper stream pools and ponds in a reed-like fashion.

The therapeutic history of the sweet flag is so long it is used in different herbal systems. In modern herbal treatment, it is commonly used as a light tonic and perfumed stimulant. Ayurveda holds it in high regard as a remedy for digestive problems as well as a rejuvenator for the head and neurological system. Its roots` other characteristics are aphrodisiac, anodyne, aromatic, carminative, diaphoretic, emmenagogue, expectorant, febrifuge, mind-altering, hypotensive, tranquilizing, stimulant, stomachal, slightly tonic, and vermifuge. It is administered internally to treat gastrointestinal issues, bronchitis, sinusitis, etc. It is claimed to have amazing tonic properties that can normalize and stimulate appetite. It is advised in the treatment of anorexia nervosa because it decreases stomach acidity in small doses while increasing stomach secretions in bigger doses. External applications of the sweet flag are used to relieve neuralgia, rheumatic discomfort, and skin outbreaks. While chewing the root helps with toothaches, a root infusion can cause an abortion. It is used as a folk treatment for a variety of dry food.

Conclusion

God has enriched the plants with countless nutritional, and amazing medicinal properties. The nutrients (carbohydrates, vitamins, minerals) of plants play an important role in the growth of the human body. Plants and herbs are the main sources of medicines from ancient times. Man cannot survive on planet Earth without plants because plants provide Oxygen (O₂) and absorb Carbon dioxide (CO₂). Oxygen (O₂) is essential for the survival of human beings while an excess of Carbon dioxide (CO₂) in the atmosphere is harmful. Plants with their medicinal effects are an integral component of Hadith literature. Herbal medicines are an essential aspect of natural treatment. Further, botanical products act as a tonic to prevent the ailment. Additionally, herbal medicines can be used in combination with conservative medicine. The cure of diseases with plants and medicines mentioned in hadith literature tends to be more tolerated than conventional medicines, having fewer side effects.

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